

EARTH SCIENCES

SEISMIC ZONING WITHIN LARGE MORPHOSTRUCTURAL UNITS OF BAIKAL REGION

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Abstract

The paper presents the geophysical and engineering-geological data obtained for the Baikal region when performing engineering surveys for large basins of the region. The probability of predicting the impact of near-surface engineering-geological section on the level of loose and rocky ground seismicity manifestation is based on the measurement of geophysical field parameters on the territory of some industrial and civil objects. The initial data substantiating engineering-geological parameters were obtained from the integrated instrumental geophysical measurements (seismic and electrical surveying methods, surveys, microseismic records) and theoretical calculations. The prediction is based on the existence of wide-ranging types of frozen ground along the entire north-south trending permafrost. The northern flank of the study area is related to the permafrost zone (Chara and Muya basins). The southern sector is the transition zone between thawed and frozen ground. The authors consider the impact of near-surface layers on seismic hazard calculation (in tabular form) for these structural elements.

Keywords: engineering-seismological parameters, climate zones, grounds, permafrost, seismic hazard, monitoring.

Introduction. The study conducted by the authors is based on the geophysical and engineering-geological data for the Baikal region of Russia. The need to predict the impact of near-surface engineering-geological section on the level of loose and rocky ground seismicity manifestation within large morphostructural objects (basins) in perennially frozen ground conditions is due to a large variety of the parameters of geophysical field within the basins and their bordering mountain systems [1].

The engineering-seismological survey technique consisted in measuring seismic hazard parameters for certain territorial complexes. The approach to seismic hazard zoning lied in implementing the following steps: 1 – assessment of seismic properties of major grounds with regard to ground conditions; 2 – choice of reference ground and assessment of its seismic parameters; 3 – separation of major ground conditions according to seismic properties relative to reference grounds; 4 – seismic hazard zoning of the area.

Seismic hazard assessment of grounds was made using seismic rigidity method and computational methods. The study of contrastingly different degrees of seismicity manifestation in permafrost areas is one the main fields of research pursued. Seismicity of these areas may differ from the initial seismicity by one intensity unit or more due to the ground, hydrological or permafrost conditions. The methods of hazard calculations refer to instrumental and computational techniques that take into account seismic rigidity variations [2], depth of occurrence of groundwater, and a temperature of the frozen layer [3].

Category 1 grounds (relatively well-preserved rocks with 3000 m/s longitudinal wave velocity and 2.5 g/cm³ bulk density) serve as a reference for calculations [1].

The unsaturated, thawed rocks with most likely velocity values are accepted as average grounds associated with the initial seismicity of the area. Shaking is one unit less intense than the initial ground shaking where the ground velocities correspond to a reference value.

In the areas under investigation, the studies have been made of several sites of existing and under construction civil and industrial facilities. These data were used to make a general seismological assessment of the areas subdivided into relatively high and low seismic and technogenic hazard zones.

Using the above approach to seismic hazard assessment, there were determined the generalized V_p and V_s values in the grounds predominant in permafrost areas.

The separation of frozen rocks into plastic frozen and hard frozen, depending on their temperature and, therefore, seismic hazard, was performed using the VES survey data. The hard frozen rocks usually have temperature lower than -2°C and a resistivity of tens of thousands ohm-m, and the plastic frozen grounds with a temperature higher than -2°C are characterized by a resistivity of up to a few thousands ohm-m. The difference in seismic hazard between these rocks is one intensity unit, and its degree is only determined by rock conditions and temperature [1, 4]. A large number of measurements obtained made it possible to cover all major grounds and compute their intensity increments relative to the chosen reference ground.

A large number of the instrumental measurements allowed assessing seismic properties of major rocks, which serve as basement rocks in construction of infrastructure facilities, and mapping seismic hazard of large structural formations of the Baikal region. The selected approach of consistent implementation of such steps as initial seismicity substantiation, technogenic and seis-

mic hazard zoning, preparing most technogenically affected sites for reliable foundations, and predicting their-related seismic effects will provide the first approximation solution for these tasks. Besides, such approach eliminates some methodical defects in seismic zoning under complex natural conditions. This will allow predicting the change of technogenic and seismic loads on the infrastructure and taking timely measures to mitigate their consequences.

The study is aimed at analysis of the geophysical and engineering-geological data for the area of three large structures (Chara, Muya and Tunka basins) with the possibility of a subsequent seismic hazard prediction for industrial and civil objects during the design, construction and operation stages. The relevance of the study is due to high seismic hazard level for the Baikal region. The initial data for this study were represented by the results of instrumental seismic measurements at locations covering the full range of engineering-geological conditions: from thawed grounds (with a probability of seasonal freezing) to perennially frozen grounds (with a probability of seasonal thawing). The experimental materials and methods served as a basis for obtaining all the necessary data (presented in tabular form) on loose-ground conditions and thickness, basic parameters of seismic ground properties, and seismic wave propagation layer velocities [5,6,7].

The Chara basin is unique in the context of permafrost distribution and high seismic hazard. The earthquake intensity in the basin, by today's standards, is estimated at 9 units or higher. The analysis of the largest seismic events in the second half of the XX century and the modern seismic data for the Chara basin shows high present-day seismic potential.

The Chara basin is a tectonic depression at the eastern flank of the Baikal rift zone. It extends for about 120 km southwest-northeast and is 20 to 35 km wide. Steep slopes of the Kodar Range bound the northwest side of the basin; on the southeast it is bounded by the Udokan Range. The basin-filling and basin-adjacent stratigraphic successions consist of different rock units: 1 – rocky ground exposures (mountainous landforms), 2 – glacial deposits (moraine landforms), 3 – present-day and Holocene basin deposits (floodplains and river terraces).

Due to its physical-geographical conditions, the basin is located in the continuous or discontinuous permafrost zone. Based on the geothermal data, the thickness of permafrost in the basin is estimated at 100 m or more at a temperature of -1.5 to $-4-6^{\circ}\text{C}$. In the mountains bordering the basin, the permafrost thickness can reach 1000 m or more (Udokan and Kodar ranges) at a temperature lower than -6°C [8].

1. The rocky grounds of this area are represented by the Lower Proterozoic sedimentary and metamorphic rocks: aleurolites and calcareous sandstones.

The intrusive rock formations represent the Early Proterozoic gabbro and different granite varieties. Among these formations is a complex of deluvial sediments. The deluvial slope deposits are composed of present-day and Late Quaternary boulders and cobbles held together by sandy loam and rubble-sandy loam soils. The deposits are up to 8 m thick. The perennially

frozen rocks on the deluvial slopes are represented by loams and sandy loams. These rocks are usually lens-shaped cryogenic structures. The upper-to-middle slope deposits of the southern exposure contain only cement. The minimal seasonal thaw depth (0.8 m) is observed at the foot of deluvial slopes of the northern exposure. On the southern slopes, the seasonal thaw depth is more than 2 m.

2. The glacial deposits are confined to the following landforms:

a) High over-floodplain terrace complex in an ancient valley represented by alluvial deposits of sand, sandy loams, pebbles, and boulders. The feature of this terrace complex deposit is the presence of various cryogenic textures and cement ice. The seasonal thaw depth reaches 1 m.

b) A complex of trough valleys filled with alluvial (sandy loam, sand, pebble) and moraine (pebble, boulder, sandy loam and sand) deposits. This type of perennially frozen ground is characterized by slightly undulating, lenticular and bread-crust cryogenic structures. The seasonal thaw depth varies from 0.6 m in the central and boggy parts to 2 m on the southern slope surfaces.

c) The basal and end moraine complex composed of perennially frozen loams and sandy loam with pebbles, boulders and sand. Small lens-shaped icy inclusions have been found in the perennially frozen moraine sediment under boulders and pebbles, held by sandy loam soil. Owing to their morphology and composition, the moraine deposits have a wide range of seasonal thaw depth – from 1 m in boggy hollows to 4 m on the slopes. The present-day and Holocene basin deposits – pebbles, sands and sandy loams (up to 30 m thick) with the presence of ice-cement or fossil ice, – can be traced within the floodplain and low over-floodplain terraces.

3. Present-day and Holocene basin deposits (riverine floodplains and terraces)

These deposits are represented by sand pebble layers up to 30 m thick, depending on morphostructural features of the microrelief in the basin; less often – by up to 2 m thick gravel-sand beds. The floodplain alluvium is composed of sands and sandy loams, sometimes of up to 2 m thick loams. The described deposits contain ice-cement from a depth of 1-5 m. There are also a few meters thick sheet-like and lens-shaped bodies of fossil ice. The temperature of permafrost varies from -2° to -5°C .

As has already been mentioned, one of the main directions for this kind of research is identification of areas with different levels of seismicity in the basin. Seismicity of these areas can be one or more units apart from initial seismicity due to the ground, hydrogeological and permafrost conditions. According to regulatory documents, the calculations were made with reference to soils such as relatively well-preserved hard rocks with longitudinal wave velocities of 3000 m/s and bulk density of 2.5 g/cm^3 . The accepted values fall within their distribution intervals for rocky grounds and, on average, are 4 times higher than the most probable ve-

localities of thawed water-unsaturated rocks. Thus, seismic intensity for the reference soils is one unit less than the 9-unit initial intensity and is set equal to 8.

Seismic works were conducted using seismic refraction (SR) to acquire P -wave velocities (V_p) and multichannel analysis of surface waves (MASW) which allows calculating seismic S -wave velocities (V_s). In the study area, there were selected the basic

stratigraphic successions which were studied using two most common geophysical methods (seismic and electrical exploration) (Fig. 1) These data contributed to comprehensive engineering-seismological assessment of the area subdivided into relatively high and low seismic hazard zones [9,10].

Fig. 1. Engineering-geological sketch map of the Chara basin. 1 – rocky grounds (mountain structures), 2 – glacial deposits (moraines), 3 – present-day and Holocene basin deposits (floodplains and river terraces); 4 – frozen ground temperatures, 5 – from the top down: P -wave velocities (V_p), S -wave velocities (V_s); 6 – shown further are seismic intensity units, 7 – locations of integrated geophysical study.

The Muya basin is located less than 100 km southwest of the Chara basin. This structure is bounded by North Muya and South Muya ranges. It is extending west-east for more than 130 km, its width reaches 40-45 km.

The basin-filling stratigraphic succession is generally comparable to that of the Chara basin. Most of the valley is covered by continuous permafrost more than

100 m thick with a temperature of -1.5 to 5°C . Taliks with deep seasonal freezing are located in the central part of the basin, the zones of permafrost up to 100 m thick with a temperature of 0 to -1.5°C occupy almost the entire intrabasinal space. In the mountains bordering the basin, the permafrost can be 500 m thick or more with a temperature up to -6°C or lower.

Table 1
Lithological complex, P -wave and S -wave velocities (V_p and V_s), ground temperatures, and incremental intensity computation.

Lithological complex	VV_p , m/s	VV_s ,m/s	t , $^{\circ}\text{C}$	ΔJ from (ρV), unit	ΔJ from (t°), unit	ΔI units
Present-day and Holocene deposits						
Floodplains and low floodplain terraces	5510 3500	3320 1900	-3,4 -2,1	0,05	0,32	0,37
High floodplain terraces	540 3290	260 1710	-1,0	0,08	0,54	0,62
High floodplain terraces	740 3750	400 2240	<-2	-0,13	0	-0,13
Glacial deposits						
Moraine complex	660 3000	1540	<-2	0	0	0
Moraine complex	700 3400		-5,5 -4,8	0,06	0	0,06
Rocky grounds						
Bedrock	2300 3100	1210 1830	-1	-1	0	-1
Bedrock	3400 4200	1890 2600	<-2	-1	0	-1

The term “permafrost degradation” is applied to the study area for the first time. Used previously for infrastructure-affected permafrost grounds, it now can be applicable also to permafrost under natural conditions. Permafrost changes are due mainly to the basin microclimate caused by physical-geographical features of the basin location.

The basin has high seismicity estimated at 9 intensity units. As already mentioned, a rocky ground in the mountains, bordering the basin, at generalized strength properties corresponds to the level of local initial seismicity for average soils (9 units). Therefore, the further results of seismic hazard assessment for the areas of other stratigraphic successions will be based on the 9-unit seismic intensity in the region.

In the rocky-ground cross-sections, the velocities are determined by different degrees of rock weathering. To a depth of 13-15 m, they are characterized by V_p values equal to 1000-1100 m/s and V_s values equal to 470-580 m/s. Slightly weathered rocks have higher V_p and V_s values, of 1690 to 2720 m/s and of 730 to 1420 m/s, respectively. The velocity increases rapidly with depth and reaches 4200 m/s. The ratio of longitudinal to transverse wave velocities varies from 1.6 for compact rock to 2.2 for disintegrated rock. The largest number of measurements for relatively well-preserved and frozen bedrock falls within the values close to 3000 m/s. The generalized V_p and V_s values in the rock varieties with composition and condition prevalent in the Muya basin are presented in table 2.

Table 2

Ground type	P - and S -wave velocities (m/s)	Thawed air-dry	Thawed water-saturated	With low-ice content $t < -0^{\circ}\text{C}$	Hard-frozen $t < -1^{\circ}\text{C}$
Sand	V_p	440-690	1500-1800	1380-2180	3200-3700
	V_s	200-330	300-600	660-1150	1620-2060
Boulders, pebble with sand	V_p	590-860	1600-1900	1980-3160	3400-3900
	V_s	270-430	360-700	980-1760	1790-2230
Bedrock	V_p	1900-2300	2300-2700	2300-3100	3400-4200
	V_s	960-1240	920-1280	1210-1830	1890-2600

The average V_p and V_s for loose sediments deposited in the basin increase with increasing frozen ground thickness. The velocity gradient decreases with depth. When the ground becomes saturated, it exhibits a sharp, 3-4 times increase in longitudinal wave velocities. The transverse wave velocities increase 1.1-1.5 times. The V_p/V_s ratio may reach 4-5 in the near-surface section, decrease with depth and be approximately 2.5 in water-saturated loose grounds.

The experimental measurements and theoretical calculations performed, as well as the engineering-geological data available, allowed drawing a sketch-map of zoning parameters of seismic effects for the Muya basin (Fig. 2). The assessment of the parameters required was

based on the accelerogram, spectral acceleration and frequency calculations for the most probable models of natural and predicted ground conditions.

In accordance with the natural (frozen) ground condition, the basin is divided into 8-9 intensity unit areas; the range of peak ground acceleration values is 160 to 370 cm/s^2 for the maximum horizontal component and 86 to 150 cm/s^2 for the vertical component. In accordance with the predicted thawing ground conditions, it is divided into 8, 9 and 10 intensity unit areas; the range of peak ground acceleration is 230 to 780 cm/s^2 for NS component and 120 to 420 cm/s^2 for Z component.

Fig. 2. Engineering-geological sketch-map of the Muya basin. 1 – rocky grounds (mountain structures), 2 – glacial deposits (moraines), 3 – present-day and Holocene basin deposits (floodplains and river terraces); 4 – frozen ground temperatures, 5 – from the top down: P -wave velocities (V_p), S -wave velocities (V_s); 6 – shown further are seismic intensity units, 7 – locations of integrated geophysical study.

The above-mentioned ranges of variation of basic seismic parameters characterize the dynamics of their changes for the total degradation of permafrost. They can be refined for the basin areas chosen for seismic hazard zoning in scale of the planned construction based on the above approaches and selected calculation technique for seismic effects.

The alternation of the Baikal-type ranges and basins of different width and length forms a single basin under the common name of Tunka which is the western

branch of the Baikal rift zone (Fig. 3). The structure is located in the southwestern flank of the Baikal Mountains and occupies an intermediate position between Lake Baikal and Lake Khubsugul in Mongolia [11].

The geological structure is contributed to by the Archean to recent rocks. The rocky grounds are represented by the Precambrian and Paleozoic rocks broken through by numerous intrusions. The basin is filled with the Paleogene-Quaternary deposits.

Fig.3. Engineering-geological sketch-map of the Tunka basin. 1 – rocky grounds (mountain structures), 2 – glacial deposits (moraines), 3 – present-day and Holocene basin deposits (floodplains and river terraces); 4 – frozen ground temperatures, 5 – from the top down: P-wave velocities (V_p), S-wave velocities (V_s); 6 – shown further are seismic intensity units, 7 – locations of integrated geophysical study.

The perennially frozen materials vary from perennially frozen grounds with island talik fields (mountains bordering the basin) to sporadic permafrost occurring within the boggy and lacustrine massifs, on the peripheries of sand massifs, and on high terraces in the form of islands with a thickness of 10-100 m and a temperature of up to -0.5 °C.

An engineering-geological aspect of the geophysical studies involved sandy grounds. The presented locations of the geophysical survey are situated on the water-unsaturated and water-saturated grounds.

As illustration is the study location in the central part of the basin. The profile begins near Albugai Settlement on the eastern slope of the Badar Massif and goes into a relatively narrow zone between the sand massif and the Koimor boggy-lacustrine complex. The profile intersects the Irkut River valley in a north-south direction and runs to the foothills of the mountains bordering of the Tunka basin on the south.

A system for seismic refraction surveying was aimed at obtaining 46 m long direct-wave, reverse and catching-up time-distance curves. Each array included 5 source points (coordinates $SOU_X = -48$ m, 0 m, 22 m, 46 m, 94 m). MASW involved one of the refraction seismograms. Such surveying system allowed obtaining the earth image to depth of about 30 m. The transverse wave velocities were interpolated between the sounding locations

Interpretation of seismic refraction survey data on 11 sounding locations in the upper 30 m thick unit showed 2-3 layers along the entire profile studied. The

uppermost 2–20 m thick layer of loose, air-dry material has anomalously low V_p values not exceeding 420 m/s and is traced along the entire profile. The second, water-saturated ground layer is distinguished almost along the entire profile (except for sounding location 11-040 where the ground is air-dry with $V_p = 570$ – 690 m/s) and is characterized by 1540 to 2050 m/s interval longitudinal wave velocity variation. The third layer is represented by frozen grounds lying at depths of 8–16 m from the surface and having longitudinal wave velocities of 2500 to 2670 m/s (sounding locations 5-019, 6-020 and 11-040). The lower boundary of the frozen ground unit was not determined by seismic surveying data.

Based on the materials of field and experimental studies, all the necessary data were obtained for loose ground conditions and thickness, basic parameters of seismic ground properties, and seismic wave propagation layer velocities for a large number of the locations within large basins of the Baikal region. When using the above-mentioned data and applying the calculation methods, consideration was given to the possibility of a general database acquisition and the impact of complex near-surface ground physical properties on the assessed seismic hazard level.

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